

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SPEECH BY WORKING ON POETIC TEXTS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Abstract: This article provides general information about improving the methodology of developing students' speech by working on poetic texts in the primary class.

Keywords: sharia, text, image, methodology, speech, education, educational system, pedagogy, methodical activity.

Introduction.

Poetry is an excellent tool for developing memory, sense of rhythm, creativity and sensitivity in children. In order for children to enjoy it, they need to learn it in the most effective and stimulating way possible. This is not difficult, as children seem particularly open to learning poetry.

All experts, and by this we mean teachers and poets, recommend a playful approach to poetry. If we have already recommended you some books for babies, now we want to give them certain recommendations so that they can start reading them or learn their poems.

Speech means the process of speaking and its result. In fact, speech is one of the highest, most complex, spiritual tasks of a person. A specific function of a person that arose as a means of mutual exchange of ideas between people in the process of social work. A person perceives objects and events in the external world with the help of sensory organs and with the help of nut. Thanks to word signaling, that is, speech, a person can perceive existence in general, mentally. Speech organs, various parts of the human body that participate in the formation of speech sounds. Active speech organs include the tongue, lips, soft palate, and passive speech organs include teeth, hard palate, and nasal cavity. There are external and internal, oral and written types of speech. External speech mainly serves the purposes of communication, so it is structured in a way that is understandable to the listeners. Self-awareness plays a very important role in thought processes. Written speech (writing and reading letters) is functionally closely related to internal speech (whispering what is to be written inside, reading without making a sound). It is known that colloquial language is considered the first guide of speech development, and it gradually improves. Colloquial language is manifested in the oral narration of the read texts.

Sharia is important in shaping children's speech. It has been proven in experiments that the memory of children who have memorized more words is much better than children who have memorized less words.

Sharia not only educates children, but also has a positive effect on the development of their memory and speech. In order for children to sing songs beautifully with intonation, the meaning of this song must first be understood. Then a poem is sung according to each hero of the poem

In the child's brain, the speech center and the computing center are close to each other. therefore, children with fluent speech who have memorized a lot can also easily do quick calculations.

A primary school teacher should focus on developing students' speaking skills by working on poetic texts in primary school.

Analyzing the text of the poem and bringing it to life through images, it is possible for the child to quickly memorize the poem and increase his love for the Sharia.

Conclusion.

Games on the development of children's speech

1. To develop listening to speech (hearing different sounds and letters) Your leader will call the letter that needs to be "caught" in the word, for example, the sound "Sh". In turn, words with the presence of this letter and without it: school, class, student, cabinet, scarf, stapler, spy, etc. Hearing the letter "Sh" in the word, the child should wave his hands. If the child finds it difficult and does not hear the required sound, the presentation should be reflected in the pronunciation.

2. The version of the previous game, without the pronunciation of the already given voice, is to place various toys in front of the child and show them the ones that contain the letter "Sh" (bear, mouse, baby Masha, ball, etc.) I ask.

3. "I believe - I don't believe" The boy tells a story: We walked in the yard. An orange was found there, growing in the sand, hairy like a watermelon. We cut it and removed the skin. But they tasted it and burned their tongues. The child should be told what the text can really be and what the invention is.

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